

Quantum Excited States

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In earlier notes, quantum mechanics was described in terms of conditional probability yielding an average kinetic energy matching classical physics:

$$\left[\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} f_p \exp(ipx) \right] / W(x) = \frac{1}{2} m v(x)v(x) \quad ((1))$$

Here $W(x)$, the wavefunction, is a normalization function and the complex conditional probability is $f_p \exp(ipx)$, with $\exp(ipx)$ representing probability associated with free motion. $v(x)$ is the classical kinetic energy. ((1)) is equivalent to the time independent Schrodinger equation. In addition, ((1)) may be written using a Fourier series for $V(x)$ (where $\frac{1}{2}mv(x)v(x)=E-V(x)$) and another for $W(x)$. This yields:

$$\frac{p^2}{2m} f_p + \sum_{k+j=p} V_j f_k = E f_p \quad ((2))$$

It was argued ((2)) represents a cycling equation, with each f_p (p plane wave) cycling in resonance with the same frequency E .

In this note, we wish to apply these ideas to excited states i.e. states above the ground state. For the quantum oscillator, the Schrodinger equation gives $E_n = \hbar \omega (n + .5)$ where ω is the classical frequency $\sqrt{k/m}$. This has the appearance of disturbances of frequency ω_n building up the excited states. In this note, we find that similar disturbances build up all excited states, as an excited wavefunction may be written as: $W_n(x) = g_n(x)W_0(x)$, where $W_0(x)$ is the ground state. The kinetic energy of the ground state is thus $E_0 - V(x)$ which together with $V(x)$ yields E_0 . This still holds for any excited state, so $g_n(x)$, it seems, forms a resonance with $W_0(x)$ which does not directly involve the potential $V(x)$.

Ground State Considerations

Quantum mechanical average kinetic and potential energy may be described in classical statistical terms by: (one dimension)

$$KE \text{ average} = \int dx W(x) \left(-\frac{1}{2m}\right) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) = \int dx W(x)W(x) \frac{1}{2} m v(x)v(x)$$

$$= \int dp f_p^* f_p \frac{p^2}{2m}$$

And

$$PE \text{ average} = \int dx V(x) W(x)W(x)$$

Here the probability density is given by $W(x)W(x)$. At this point, one may ask why one expresses probability density in terms of its square root $W(x)$. It seems $W(x)$ is related to conditional probability which leads to an equation for $W(x)$ and energy levels namely ((1)). This conditional probability equation already links quantum mechanics to classical physics by the use of $.5mv(x)v(x)= E - V(x)$.

Writing the Schrodinger equation using Fourier transforms, leads to ((2)), a cycling equation, showing that each fp cycles with the same frequency E_n . Thus, this cycling occurs for the ground state as well as excited states. It seems, however, that excited states can be described in terms of a resonance of an "excitation" with the ground state.

Excited States

Consider writing an excited state as $W_n(x)= g_n(x) W_0(x)$. For the oscillator, $W_0(x)$ is of the form $\exp(-.5 \sqrt{km} x^2)$ and $g_n(x)=H_n(bx)$ where $H_n(bx)$ is the nth Hermite polynomial and b is a constant depending on m and k . One may ask: what is the meaning of $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ in such a case? It becomes $[W_0(x)W_0(x)][g_n(x)g_n(x)]$ which is an "and" probability i.e. the probability to be at x due to the ground state times the probability to be at x for an excitation, described by $g_n(x)$. At this point, one may argue this description is completely arbitrary and that one is forcing an "and" probability picture.

The reason for writing $W_n(x)$ as $g_n(x)W_0(x)$ follows from the idea that the kinetic energy term $(-1/2m) [d/dx d/dx W(x)]/W(x)$ must yield constant $- V(x)$. $W_0(x)$ already guarantees such a form, namely $E_0 - V(x)$. The only problem is that E_0 , the ground state energy, is lower than the excited energy. Thus, the excitation $g_n(x)$, should yield kinetic energy $E-E_0$. This is the energy of a photon or phonon needed to excite the level. To see the details consider:

$$(-1/2m) [d/dx d/dx W(x)]/W(x) = (-1/2m) [1/ g_n(x)W_0(x)] [\{d/dx d/dx g_n(x)\} W_0(x) + g_n(x)\{ d/dx d/dx W_0(x)\} + 2 \{d/dx g_n(x)\} \{ d/dx W_0(x)\}]$$

$$= (E_0-V(x)) + \{d/dx d/dx g_n(x)\} / g_n(x) + 2 \{d/dx g_n(x)\} \{ d/dx W_0(x)\} / W_0(x) g_n(x) \quad ((3))$$

Thus:

$$(E_n-E_0) g_n(x) = \{d/dx d/dx g_n(x)\} + 2 \{d/dx g_n(x)\} \{ d/dx W_0(x)\} / W_0(x) \quad ((4))$$

For the quantum oscillator, this leads to the Hermite equation because $\{ d/dx W_0(x)\} / W_0(x) = -4 \sqrt{km} x (-1/2m)$. Thus, one may see the classical frequency $w=\sqrt{k/m}$ immediately appearing. We argue that ((4)) should also apply to other cases and point out that photons and phonons appear experimentally as agents of excitation of quantum states.

Equation ((4)) is interesting for two reasons. First, the potential $V(x)$ is completely absent indicating that the excitation $g_n(x)$ does not directly interact with the potential. It does, however, interact indirectly because it interacts with $W_0(x)$, the ground state, which directly depends on the potential. Secondly, ((4)) is of the form of a type of Schrodinger equation except for the fact that $V(x) W_0(x)$ is replaced by $2 \{d/dx g_n(x)\} \{d/dx W_0(x)\} / W_0(x)$ which is a kind of velocity dependent potential. Thus, if E in the Schrodinger equation represents a frequency $\exp(iEt)$, then one may argue that $E_n - E_0$ in ((4)) also represents a frequency as this has the appearance of a resonance equation.

Consider a description in terms of classical force. From the Schrodinger equation one has:

$$d/dx \{ [(-1/2m) d/dx d/dx W(x)] / W(x) \} = F(x) \quad ((5))$$

We see from ((4)) that the kinetic energy may be written as:

$E_0 - V(x) + (E_n - E_0)$. Thus, the $(E_n - E_0)$ piece from $g_n(x)$ disappears under the action of d/dx and it is not linked to force.

It should also be noted that:

$$(-1/2m) d/dx d/dx W(x) / W(x) = .5 m v(x)v(x)$$

Consider the oscillator case. Then $x = \sqrt{2E/k} \cos(\omega t)$ and $v = \omega \sqrt{2E/k} \sin(\omega t)$. Thus, the kinetic energy behaves in a periodic manner namely $\sin(\omega t)\sin(\omega t)$. Both $W_0(x)$ and $g_n(x)$ contribute to this periodicity as W_0 can only contribute $.5\omega - .5 kx^2 = .5 \hbar \omega - .5k 2E/k \cos(\omega t)\cos(\omega t)$. In order to have the full periodicity of $\sin(\omega t)\sin(\omega t)$, $g_n(x)$ needs to contribute $E_n - E_0 = \hbar \omega n$.

Picture of $g_n(x)$

It has been argued that $g_n(x)$ contributes to the kinetic energy $.5mv(x)v(x)$, but does not directly interact with $V(x)$. It is interesting to note from ((3)) and ((4)), that $g_n(x)$ contributes $E_n - E_0$ to the kinetic energy which is not dependent on x . Is there a classical picture that might help picture the kinetic energy of $g_n(x)$? One may note that in quantum mechanics, there are two average velocities. One is the root mean square velocity $v(x)$, which matches the classical velocity. It is given by the square root of $2m$ times $(-1/2m) [d/dx d/dx W(x)] / W(x)$. There is also a flux velocity $u(x)$ given by $[d/dx W(x)]/W(x)$. This is related to $d/dx [W(x)W(x)]$, the change in spatial density and may be written as: $[\sum \text{over } p \text{ } f_p \text{ } \exp(ipx)] / W(x)$ and so is a kind of p average. Thus, ((3)) seems to be of the form: $[v(x)^2 + v_g(x)^2 + 2 u(x) u_g(x)]$. Here $v_g(x)$ is the rms velocity associated with $g_n(x)$ and $u_g(x)$, its flux velocity. This is almost of the form of $[v+v_g]^2$, i.e. a kind of addition of velocities although $v(x)$ and $u(x)$ are not the same and neither are $v_g(x)$ and $u_g(x)$.

It should also be pointed out, that the overall cycling resonance equation ((2)) should apply for any state, ground or excited. Thus, one could consider an excited state and write:

$$p^2/2m + \sum_{j+k=p} V_k f_k = E_n$$

Here, one has not separated $W_n(x)$ into $W_0(x)g_n(x)$. Thus, there is an overall cycling occurring with frequency E_n . E_n is much larger than E_0 , so the cycling time is smaller. Using $W_0(x)g_n(x)$, one has a cycling time for $W_0(x)$, namely $1/E_0$, at the same time $g_n(x)$ and $W_0(x)$ are forming a resonance together with a frequency of $E-E_0$. This may seem a little strange, but it appears to be consistent with a photon or phonon being absorbed. In such a case, the photon or phonon has the frequency of cycling time of $1/(E-E_0)$, but the ground state that absorbs it, another frequency E_0 with cycling time $1/E_0$. In the case of the harmonic oscillator, both are proportional to $w=\sqrt{k/m}$, the classical frequency.

Oscillator Case

For the case of the oscillator, equation ((4)) contains the term $2 \frac{d}{dx} (\exp(-.5 \sqrt{km} x^2) \frac{d}{dx} g_n(x) / \exp(-.5 \sqrt{km} x^2))$. The $u(x)$ of the ground state yields a value of \sqrt{km} and this leads to $E-E_0$ being of the form: $\hbar w n$ where n is an interger and $w=\sqrt{k/m}$. This is interesting as w is the mechanical frequency of an oscillator, but it is proportional to the frequency of the disturbance.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems one may describe a quantum excited state as $W_0(x)g_n(x)$ because $W_0(x)$ interacts directly with the potential $V(x)$. In particular, $KE = (-1/2m) \{ \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) \} / W(x)$ yields a term: $(-1/2m) \{ \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_0(x) \} / W_0(x) = E_0 - V(x)$. Thus, $W_0(x)$ suffices to eliminate $V(x)$ and the kinetic energy terms containing $g_n(x)$ yield (E_n-E_0) . Thus, $g_n(x)$ has the appearance of an oscillation (see equation ((4))) which does not directly interact with the potential $V(x)$, but supplies the extra needed energy (in the form of kinetic energy) to bring E_0 to E_n . By the form of equation ((4)), E_n-E_0 should be a cycling frequency, suggesting that $g_n(x)$ may be associated with a physical frequency, say that of a photon or phonon.